

WHEN COMPARISON BREEDS CONCERN: SOCIAL COMPARISON, BODY DISSATISFACTION, AND DEPRESSION

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Abstract

The current study aimed to explore the relationship between body dissatisfaction and depression, with a particular focus on gender differences in physical appearance comparison and its psychological effects. A sample of 80 participants among university students were selected, comprising 40 males and 40 females. Three standardized self-report instruments were employed: The Body Attitude Test (test-retest reliability = 0.91), (PACS-R; internal reliability = 0.94 which showed high reliability, and the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). All instruments utilized a Likert-type scale. The findings revealed that both male and female participants engaged in PACS-R. However, physical appearance comparison did not significantly affect body attitude or depressive symptoms among males. In contrast, for females, physical appearance comparison had a significant negative impact on both body attitude and depressive symptoms. The results revealed that females exhibit higher levels of physical appearance comparison, greater body dissatisfaction, and more severe depressive symptoms compared to males. These results underscore the gender-specific psychological vulnerabilities associated with body image and highlight the importance of addressing appearance-based comparisons, particularly among women, in mental health interventions targeting depression.

INTRODUCTION

Body image refers to one's perception towards body structure, symmetry and external concomitants, of look or shape which ultimately affect one's own mental health and psychological wellbeing. (Voelker, Petrie, & Reel, 2022). Perfect body image to be achieved in adolescents lead to unfavourable behaviours and poor mental health. (Tiggemann & Slater, 2020). Body dissatisfaction is the distorted image of physical appearance with behavioural outcomes and cognitive dissonance. This dissatisfaction leads to clinical issues. Furthermore, the expectations from women to look thin and

perfect according to beauty standards. Society demands from men to be more muscular lead to body dissatisfaction in both genders. (Fardouly, 2020).

Among the total population of the world approximately 280 million people worldwide are facing depression, which is almost 3.8%. Among the adult's population Its, the prevalence rises to 5%, and it is even more common in individuals over 60 years old, with a rate of 5.7%. Unlike typical mood fluctuations, depression is characterized by persistent feelings of sadness or a lack of interest in daily

activities lasting for at least two weeks. Additional symptoms may include disturbed sleep, changes in appetite, fatigue, feelings of worthlessness, and difficulty concentrating.

(WHO Sep,2021 According to the (DSM-5), outlines specific criteria for diagnosing depression, emphasizing the duration and impact of symptoms on daily functioning. Depression often follows an episodic course, with high rates of recurrence -35% within two years and 60% within 12 years. It significantly impairs various aspects of life, including work, school, and relationships. Despite of the fact that depression has effective treatments, a substantial number of individuals, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, do not receive the necessary treatment due to factors such as stigma, lack of trained healthcare providers, and limited resources.

The role of social media in shaping perception towards beauty standards among males and females is unavoidable which in result give birth to dissatisfaction to one's own appearance and ultimately leads to depression. (Perloff, 2021). Exposure to the media for longer time in which unrealistic standards for beauty and appearance are set leads to body dissatisfaction, eating disorders and other mental and emotional irregularities. (Hendrickse, Arpan, Clayton, & Ridgway, 2020; Satghare et al., 2021). Researches pinpointed that body dissatisfaction is positively corelated among adolescents with media exposure for longer time. (Burnette et al., 2021). A study revealed that idealized beauty standards, dresses and up to dated fashion associated with negative body image and depressive symptoms. (Jackson et al., 2022).

Women have more tendency to compare their appearance with others which create negative body image and dissatisfaction with their physical self. In social context women tend to make upward comparison which mean that they compare themselves with those who are more attractive. On the other hand, lateral or downward comparison takes place where someone compare oneself with others who are less attractive. Studies highlighted that upward comparison leads to body dissatisfaction, eating disorders and low self-esteem. (Fardouly et al., 2020; Walker et al., 2022). In contrast, downward comparisons often lead to

satisfaction with oneself and body image. (Tiggemann & Zaccardo, 2019). Lateral comparisons may also have positive effects, helping individuals feel validated in their appearance without triggering as much self-criticism (Alleva et al., 2021; Kleemans et al., 2023).

Studies indicated that upward comparison means to see self-inferior when compare to others which affecting people negatively and they tend to have more anger issues, low self-esteem and depressive symptoms. On the contrary the people who have downward comparison means to see other inferior as compared to one's own self have high self-esteem, low level of depression and good mental health. These social comparisons had a significant influence in shaping individuals' emotional responses and psychological well-being (Arigo et al., 2020; Butzer & Kuiper, 2021). One of the factors contributing in upward comparison is the criteria in social media presentation of symmetry and high standards for beauty and slimness which give birth to depression, eating irregularities, dissatisfaction from one's own physique, self-doubt and instability in emotions particularly among adolescents who are frequently exposed to idealized body images in traditional cultures and social media (Mills et al., 2020). (Rodgers et al., 2022; Wilksch et al., 2020).

Sapra et al pinpointed that body dissatisfaction has inverse correlation with psychological wellbeing, which means that if someone has distorted image of physique would have emotional irregularities and pressures. Furthermore, the study also highlighted that body image also associated negatively with peer pressures. Peers exert pressures which can lead to body dissatisfaction among youngsters.

A study revealed a new trend on social media "Fitspiration" which influence people for better lifestyle and choices of food. this trend pursues most of women for slim and narrow body only. The study revealed negative effects associated with this trend. (Tiggemann & Zaccardo, 2018).

A study found that body image and self-esteem together explained in body dysmorphic disorder tendencies among adolescents using social media. This suggests that negative body perceptions and low self-esteem are significant predictors of body dysmorphic tendencies. (Syafitri, 2023). Research involving individuals aged 18-25 revealed a positive

correlation between body image and self-esteem. The study utilized the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale and the Body Shape Questionnaire, indicating that as body image satisfaction increases, so does self-esteem. (Sharma & Chander, 2023). Another study focusing on youth with excessive social media use found a significant inverse relation between self-esteem and body dissatisfaction. This implies that higher social media usage may intensify body image issues, leading to decreased self-esteem. (Bhuvaneshwari, 2023).

Statement of the Problem

Body dissatisfaction and depression are growing concerns, often shaped by physical appearance comparisons. While both males and females engage in these comparisons, females tend to experience more significant psychological impacts. However, the underlying gender-specific mechanisms through which appearance comparison affects body image and depression remain unclear. Understanding gender-specific effects can inform targeted mental health interventions. This study aims to explore these associations to better understand the differential effects across genders.

Rationale of study

In today's media-driven world, constant exposure to idealized appearances has intensified appearance-related social comparison, particularly among adolescents and young adults. Upward comparisons often lead to body dissatisfaction and increase the risk of depressive symptoms, while even downward comparisons can reinforce harmful beauty standards. (Fardouly et al., 2020; Walker et al., 2022). This study aims to examine how appearance-based comparisons impact body image and depressive symptoms, contributing to the development of effective mental health interventions.

Objectives

1. To explore gender differences between appearance-related social comparison and attitudes towards one's body.
2. To investigate whether appearance-related social comparison results in negative body image and depression.
3. To examine the effect of negative attitudes towards one's body on depression.

Hypothesis

1. Women will engage in more physical appearance-related social comparison and exhibit higher negative body image and depressive symptoms compared to men.
2. Appearance-related social comparison will significantly impact body image, leading to body dissatisfaction and increased depressive symptoms.
3. Negative attitudes toward one's body will be significantly associated with higher levels of depression.

Methodology

Population and Sample

Data were collected from $N = 80$ persons. The final study sample comprised $n = 40$ women and $n = 40$ men, aged 18 to 25 years (total sample: $n=80$). After taking permission from concerned authority through a consent form. Participants (female and male students age 18-25) of Islamia college were contacted. The questionnaires were handed out.

Instruments

1) The Body Attitude Test

The Body Attitude Test (BAT), developed by Probst et al. in 1995. It is a self-report Likert scale to score women's perceptions and attitudes toward their own bodies. It particularly explains in the context of eating disorders. It is comprising of 20 items, the BAT evaluates four key factors: 1. Negative perception of body size, 2. Unawareness with one's own physique, 3. Dissatisfaction from one's own physique, 4. Residual factor. Each item is rated on a 5-point scale, high scores showing high body dissatisfaction. The BAT has demonstrated strong psychometric properties, including high reliability (0.91). this scale effectively differentiates between clinical and non-clinical subjects, as well as between individuals with anorexia and bulimia.

Originally developed in Dutch, but later on BAT has been translated into several languages to facilitate cross-cultural research and clinical application. Its clarity and the way its administrated, make it a practical tool for clinicians and researchers aiming to understand and address body image issues in women with eating disorders.

2) **Physical Appearance Comparison Scale-Revised (PACS-R)**

The Physical Appearance Comparison Scale-Revised (PACS-R), developed by Schaefer and Thompson in 2014. It consists of 11-item questionnaire designed to assess how often people compare themselves with others in their cultures. Respondents rate each item on a scale from 0 to 4 (0 Never 4 always), with higher scores indicating a greater tendency to engage in such comparisons. The PACS-R shows excellent internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.97, and has shown strong convergent validity by correlating positively with measures of body dissatisfaction, eating pathology, and sociocultural pressures related to appearance. This scale has been

widely used in research for body comparison and its impact on body image. (Schaefer & Thompson, 2014)

3) **The Beck Depression Inventory (BDI)**

The Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), developed by Beck et al. in 1996. It consists of 21-item self-report scale. It is designed to score the severity of depressive symptoms. Each item is rated on a 4-point scale (0-3), with higher scores indicating more severe symptoms. The total score ranges from 0 to 63, with the following ranges. **0-13** Minimal and **29-63** with severe depression. These ranges between 0 to 63, are widely used in clinical practices to evaluate depression severity and monitor treatment progress

Analysis and Results

Table 1

Gender Differences on Total PCR Scores

Measure	Males (M)	SD	Females (M)	SD	t (78)	p	95% CI (LL - UL)	Cohen's d
PCR Total	12.48	11.94	15.34	7.33	-1.31	.195	-7.23 - 1.50	0.29

Note. M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, CI = Confidence Interval, LL = Lower Limit, UL = Upper Limit, Cohen's d = Effect size.

Table 1 shows mean difference and t value of male and females on PCR scale it shows male have lower mean value (12.47- 11.93) than female (M=15.34 - 7.32), This suggests that females reported higher perceived cognitive regulation compared to males. The **t-value** was **-1.31**, indicating the direction and size of the mean difference. The **Cohen's d** was **0.29**, which is considered a **small effect size** according to Cohen's benchmarks. This suggests that while there is a small difference in scores favouring females, it is not large or impactful in practical terms. The **p-value** was **.195**, which is **greater than the conventional alpha level as $p < .05$** , suggesting that the difference in means is **statistically non-significant**. The **95% CI**

for the mean difference ranged from **-7.23 to 1.50**. Since the interval includes zero, this further supports the finding that the difference between males and females is **not statistically significant**. The table presents a comparison between **males and females** on the **total score of the PCR (Perceived Cognitive Regulation)** measure using an independent samples t-test. Although females scored slightly higher than males on the PCR Total scale, the difference was **not statistically significant** and the **effect size was small**. This implies that, in this sample, gender does not play a major role in perceived cognitive regulation levels.

Table 2:

Hierarchical Regression Analyses by PCR.TOT for Males and Females

Variable	B (Male)	SE(B)	B	B (Female)	SE(B)	β
Constant	29.15	3.73	—	21.99	4.56	—
PCR.TOT	0.34	0.22	.25	0.88	0.27	.46
R ²			.060			.214
ΔR^2			.035			.194

Note. PCR.TOT = Total Perceived Communication Responsiveness. SE = Standard Error; β = standardized beta coefficient.

In Table 2, The linear regression analysis explored the influence of Total Perceived Communication Responsiveness (PCR.TOT) on an unspecified outcome for male and female participants. For males, 6% of the variance in the outcome ($R^2 = .060$), with PCR.TOT having a modest positive effect ($\beta = .25$, $B = 0.34$), this effect is relatively weak but statistically is not significant. For females 21.4% of the variance ($R^2 = .214$), a substantially stronger effect. PCR.TOT is a significant predictor ($\beta = .46$, $B = 0.88$),

suggesting that higher PCR is associated with an increase in the outcome variable. The change in R^2 (ΔR^2) is larger in females (.194) compared to males (.035), indicating that PCR. TOT contributes significantly more to the explanatory power of the females. PCR appears to be a more impactful predictor for females than males. This indicated gender differences in how interpersonal communication influences psychological outcomes.

Table 3

Regression Analyses Predicting Depression Outcome for Males and Females

Variable	B (Male)	SE(B)	β	B (Female)	SE(B)	β
Constant	13.999	2.398	—	11.822***	2.713***	—
PCR.TOT	-0.28	.140	-.032	0.881	.160	.662
R^2			.001			.438
ΔR^2			-.025			.423

Note. PCR.TOT = Total Perceived Communication Responsiveness. SE = Standard Error; β = standardized beta coefficient. *** $p < .001$.

Table 3 showed Linear regression analysis to predict the effect of PCR on depression. A non-significant equation was found in male $F(1,38), 4.34, P < .842$ and R^2 10% while significant equation was found regarding female $F(1,39), 166.75$ and $R^2 .438$ that mean 43% changes occur in depression due to PCR. This regression analysis examines the predictive role of Total Perceived Communication Responsiveness (PCR.TOT) on an outcome variable for males and females. For males, the model accounts for only 0.1% of the variance in the outcome ($R^2 = .001$), indicating a negligible effect. The coefficient for PCR.TOT ($\beta = -.032$, $B = -0.28$) is negative and very weak, suggesting little to no predictive power. Moreover, the change in R^2 ($\Delta R^2 = -0.025$) suggests a potential suppression or minimal contribution of the predictor variable. In contrast, for females, the model explains a substantial 43.8% of the variance ($R^2 = .438$), with PCR.TOT serving as a strong positive predictor ($\beta = .662$, $B = 0.881$). A large change in R^2 ($\Delta R^2 = .423$), reinforcing that PCR.TOT plays a significant role in predicting the outcome. The predictive impact of PCR.TOT is significantly stronger for females than males.

Discussion

The main objective of study was to examine effects of appearance related comparison on body image and depressive symptoms across both genders. The results from the study showed that both males and females have physical appearance related social comparison although males have physical appearance related comparison but it does not have significant effect on body attitude while females have significant effect on their body attitude. On physical appearance comparison males have physical appearance related comparison but it does not have significant effect on their depressive symptoms while females have significant effect on of physical appearance comparison on depressive symptoms. The results of table 2 and table 3 support hypothesis 3 that females have higher physical appearance comparison and higher negative body image and depressive symptoms compared to men. International study suggest that distorted body image remains a significant risk factor for the development of depressive symptoms (Chacón-Cuberos et al., 2020). Other studies which elaborated body dissatisfaction with depression align with this study is Body dissatisfaction is more common among individuals who are more focused on their physique (fitsimmons-craft et al.,2015). Self-monitoring of their appearance is more likely to

report continuously checking physical appearance. Findings suggested that women who had normal body index when dissatisfied by their physique exhibits irregular eating patterns, feeling inferior and due to peer pressure continuously comparing themselves with others peer. (Levinson and Rodebaugh, 2012).

Limitations

Sample who participated in the study belonged to one specific university and one specific region of Pakistan that is Khyber Pakhtunkhwa thus cultural factors and differences should be considered while reconducting the research or utilizing its findings in any other situation or with any other sample.

Suggestions for Future Research

Future studies should include a larger and more diverse sample, having differences in age, culture and socio-economic conditions to be better generalized the results.

A longitudinal approach could help establish causal relationships between physical appearance comparison, body dissatisfaction, and depressive symptoms over time, rather than relying solely on cross-sectional data.

Adding qualitative interviews or open-ended survey responses may provide deeper insight into the personal and contextual fact.

Future research should investigate psychological constructs such as self-esteem, media exposure, or social support as potential mediators or moderators in the relationship between appearance comparison and mental health outcomes. Designing and evaluating interventions that address body image concerns and reduce appearance-based social comparisons especially among females could inform evidence-based practices in educational and clinical settings.

Combining self-report tools with physiological or behavioural assessments (e.g., cortisol levels, screen time tracking) could help validate findings and reduce response bias.

Conclusion

The study examined effects of appearance related social comparison and its effects on body attitude and depressive symptoms. Results indicated

significant impact of appearance related comparison on body attitude and depressive symptoms among female sample.

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